

STUDIES OF NITRO-*m*-CRESOLS AND THEIR HALOGEN DERIVATIVES.
PART I. 6-BROMO-2:4-DINITRO- AND 4-BROMO-2:4-DINITRO-*m*-CRESOLS

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6-Bromo-2:4-dinitro-*m*-cresol and 4-bromo-2:6-dinitro-*m*-cresol have been prepared and their constitution confirmed.

The melting point of 6-bromo-2:4-dinitro-*m*-cresol as given in literature (Kährmann, and Rust, *Annalen*, 1898, 308, 29; Gibbs and Robrtson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 105, 1891; Raiford and Leavell, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 36, 1498) is 115°, whereas we have found it to be 106°. The melting point of 4-bromo-2:6-dinitro-*m*-cresol as found by us is nearly the same as that given in literature. Of the three bromodinitro-*m*-cresols, Sane and Joshi (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 299) have shown that 2-bromo-4:6-dinitro-*m*-cresol melts at 115°. On bromination and subsequent nitration of *m*-cresol two monobromodinitro-*m*-cresols have been obtained by us, one melting at 106° and the other at 78°. The latter has also been obtained by brominating 6-nitro-*m*-cresol and subsequent nitration of 4-bromo-6-nitro-*m*-cresol so obtained, which proves its constitution to be 4-bromo-2:6-dinitro-*m*-cresol. The constitution of the other bromodinitro-*m*-cresol melting at 106° is consequently 6-bromo-2:4-dinitro-*m*-cresol. The three bromodinitro-*m*-cresols have the following characteristics (Table I).

TABLE I

Compound.	M. p.	Colour.	Solubility.	Acetyl, m.p.
4-Bromo-2:6-dinitro- <i>m</i> -cresol	78°	Colorless, pale yellow when moist	More in alcohol, less in acetic acid	96°
6-Bromo-2:4-dinitro- <i>m</i> -cresol	106°	Orange	Less in alcohol, more in acetic acid	81°
2-Bromo-4:6-dinitro- <i>m</i> -cresol	115°	Light brown	—	85-86°

EXPERIMENTAL

6-Bromo-2:4-dinitro-*m*-cresol.—*m*-Cresol (108 g.), dissolved in acetic acid (100 c.c.), was treated with bromine (160 g.) dissolved in acetic acid (200 g.). The mixture was well shaken and cooled during the addition and washed rapidly with water to remove hydrobromic acid. The insoluble liquid so obtained was mixed with strong H₂SO₄ (400 c.c., *d* 1.58), cooled and treated with HNO₃ (200 c.c., *d* 1.34) dropwise with vigorous shaking and the temperature was not allowed to rise above 40°. After standing overnight, it was heated on a water-bath till nitrous fumes ceased to evolve. On treatment with water a semi-solid, dark red product separated out. On crystallisation from alcohol it gave orange-yellow crystals (80-90 g.), m.p. 106°. (Found: Br, 28.39%. C₇H₆O₆N₂Br

requires Br, 28.88 per cent). On acetylation it gives an acetate, m.p. 81° and on benzylation, a benzoate, m.p. 103°

4-Bromo-2:6-dinitro-m-cresol.—(i). The alcoholic filtrate from above on treating with water gave a thick reddish brown liquid which on crystallisation from acetic acid yielded white leaflets (20-30 g.), m.p. 78° . (Found : Br, 28.49. $C_7H_5O_5N_2Br$ requires Br, 28.88 per cent). On acetylation it yields an acetate, m.p. 96° and on benzylation, a benzoate, m.p. 121° .

The same products were obtained when bromo-*m*-cresols were nitrated at 5° - 10° except that the relative proportion of the yield of the two products was reversed.

(ii). 6-Nitro-*m*-cresol (5 g.), dissolved in acetic acid (5 c.c.), was treated dropwise with vigorous shaking with bromine (5.2 g.), dissolved in acetic acid (10 c.c.) and of 4-bromo-6-nitro-*m*-cresol (6.5 g.) so obtained, 2 g. of it were dissolved in acetic acid and treated with a mixture of HNO_3 (5 c.c., d 1.34) and H_2SO_4 (8 c.c., d 1.58) with vigorous shaking and then treated as mentioned above when crystals (2 g.) from acetic acid of m.p. 78° were obtained.

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